

OFFICE OF ASTRONOMY
FOR DEVELOPMENT

PROJECT HIGHLIGHTS

Astronomy for a Better World

Acknowledgements: The content in this booklet is based on project reports, websites, press releases, and published articles. Images are courtesy of the projects unless otherwise stated.

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SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT GOALS

ABOUT

Astronomy and space enjoy near-universal fascination. The study of the universe is deeply connected to what it means to be human. Questions on the origin of life, the existence of life outside Earth, and exploration of other worlds stoke fundamental curiosity in people, regardless of age, gender, geography or social and economic backgrounds.

While astronomy, as a curiosity-driven science, may be seen as irrelevant to everyday life, nothing could be farther from the truth. Some of the biggest technological breakthroughs of the past few hundred years originated from basic science research, including astronomy.

Astronomy has huge potential to be used for the benefit of society given that it connects science, technology, and culture. The Office of Astronomy for Development (OAD) is a global office mandated to use astronomy, including its practitioners, skills and infrastructures, to drive positive developmental change. The office is a joint partnership between the International Astronomical Union (IAU) and the South African National Research Foundation (NRF) with the support of the Department of Science and Innovation (DSI). The OAD's vision is "Astronomy for a better world" with the 17 United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (see previous page) as broad objectives for global development.

The OAD, through an annual, open call for proposals, funds ideas that employ astronomy in innovative ways to help solve a problem or challenge in a community and promote sustainable development. Since the first call in 2012, a total of € 851,959 has been awarded to more than 150 projects across the globe. These projects have educated, inspired, and amazed children and adults, promoted dialogue and peaceful intention between communities, stimulated the local economy, encouraged inclusive practices, and so much more. Despite the small scale nature of these projects, they have managed to reach thousands globally and benefited people by leveraging the strengths of astronomy.

This booklet provides examples of projects, run by passionate, active, and knowledgeable volunteer teams, that are changing lives around the world. These projects represent only a fraction of the work being carried out globally, including a large number of activities outside OAD and IAU networks that may not be well-known.

We hope that these projects and their stories can serve to demonstrate that astronomy is not merely an academic pursuit but can induce direct, real-world benefits. We also hope that these examples stimulate further ideas that put science to work in order to enhance global development. Finally, it is our sincere belief that astronomy is just one piece of the puzzle and that we must truly embrace interdisciplinary work to produce effective change and promote sustainable development.

– THE OAD TEAM, JANUARY 2020

ASTRONOMY FOR HIMALAYAN LIVELIHOOD CREATION INDIA

Science and technology are viewed as drivers of growth and development in the long run. This project is an example of technology and astronomy creating tangible impact in a small community.

In 2016, the OAD was contacted by the Global Himalayan Expedition (GHE), a sustainable tourism organization whose mission is to provide renewable energy access to millions of people still living without any electricity. GHE conducts expeditions to unelectrified villages in remote areas, bringing together responsible travelers to build solar powered grids for these communities. To date, GHE

has electrified more than 100 villages in the mountainous regions of northern India.

With electrification plugging a basic infrastructure gap, the project turned to tourism, which is becoming increasingly popular in the region, to boost local economic growth. As it is not common for tourists to go off the beaten track, GHE

devised a plan to attract tourists to these remote communities using astronomy.

They combined the ideas of Homestays and Astro-tourism to create '**AstroStays**'. The opportunity to stargaze in clear night skies entices tourists to visit the remote community, where trained locals run stargazing sessions. Tourists can then stay the night in local Homestays, accommodation created in the homes of the villagers, and experience authentic, local culture. Astro-tourism and Homestays provide two different but linked sources of revenue to the community.

In phase-1 of the project, 30 women from 15 different villages of Ladakh were trained on basic astronomy and telescope operations. The first Astro-homestay was set up near Pangong lake in the village of Maan, where a team of 5 trained community members conduct night sky watching sessions for the incoming tourists. The telescope facility has attracted a lot of tourists and created a new economic opportunity for the community. Around 680 people visited the facility over

3 months in the (northern) summer of 2019, generating a revenue of \$1410 for the local community. (To put this in context, the average annual income here is less than \$2000.).

A second telescope was installed in the city of Leh, hosted by PAGIR, an organization working with specially-abled people. GHE partnered with PAGIR to promote inclusive Astro-tourism. PAGIR's 5 member team, trained in astronomy and telescope operations, are now conducting night viewing sessions for the tourists, creating a new channel of revenue for the organization.

The success of this intervention and its immense potential for economic mobilization of communities has motivated the OAD to include AstroStays as a project under the Flagship program on 'Astronomy for sustainable, local socio-economic development'. The OAD and the GHE will be working together to identify sites or communities who would directly benefit from the combination of electrification, tourism and astronomy.

10 REDUCED
INEQUALITIES

AD ASTRA ACADEMY BRAZIL

Ad Astra Academy exploits curiosity, an essential human trait, to promote inquiry-based learning. The program runs specific, impactful activities to spark academic interest and sustain motivation in students, especially those in under-resourced, poorer regions of the world.

In 2018, the OAD funded Ad Astra Academy to run its second edition in Brazil. The team, composed of scientists from Brazil and overseas, selected 20 students from Rio de Janeiro's City of God and Gardenia Azul favelas for this intervention run over several

months. Selected students had a range of academic interests and performances, and susceptibility to dropping out of school.

The students were first taken on field trips to the Museum of Astronomy and

Rio planetarium. These trips already had an effect on the students, one of whom commented, "Here I can learn stuff I never even thought about studying". Over one week, they engaged in a hands on curriculum on the theme of planetary habitability and learned to use the scientific method in real-world settings. Students explored the coast with an underwater drone, conducted experiments, and explored Mars through augmented reality. The week ended in a capstone project centered around the use of real Mars rover mission data to plan investigations of a Martian crater's habitability and ancient environmental conditions. The students built small model rovers to understand fundamental engineering and design principles and ultimately pitched their rover traverse plans via a Skype call with Mars Science Laboratory team members at NASA.

The hands-on curriculum was followed by one week of coursework to consolidate gains. In order to help retain students in science and support them pursue higher education, two of the students were provided scholarships to work at the Museum of Life.

While there are a multitude of systemic factors that need to change to create long-lasting impact, analysis of pre- and post-tests indicated that such brief, impactful interventions can play a positive role in a student's educational trajectory.

The project was supported by several local institutions such as the National Museum, the Center for Mineral Technology (CETEM), Instituto Presbiteriano Álvaro Reis (INPAR), the Federal University of Rio de Janeiro (UFRJ), the Museum of Astronomy, Rio's Planetarium, and the Museum of Life.

ASTROLAB: STARLIGHT IN THE UNIVERSITY LAB SUB-SAHARAN AFRICA

Astrolab is a low cost research tutorial, pioneered by Profs. Michele Gerbaldi and Jean-Pierre de Grève, for universities in need of astronomy infrastructure and curriculum.

Astrolab leverages on the excitement and accessibility of astronomy to teach undergraduate students the primary steps involved in physics research and the scientific method – observation, image acquisition, processing, data analysis and writing up results. It uses remote telescopes accessible over the internet to circumvent the need for dedicated and expensive research infrastructure. Thus, it lowers the entry barrier for astronomy in universities, especially in developing countries.

Students plan and perform real-time observations with these robotic telescopes and transform those observations into a scientific result under the guidance of tutors. After several successful OAD-supported workshops for students as well as trainers, Astrolab has established a managerial team to take over the operational aspects. This consortium is developing an online platform for exchanging best practices and remote training, as well as a monitoring system.

A notable success story of this project is the University of Zululand, a historically disadvantaged university in South Africa, which was a recipient of Astrolab training. The university is now developing an undergraduate astronomy curriculum and installing a small, optical teaching telescope.

Astrolab is an education partner of the Las Cumbres Observatory (LCO) and receives telescope time on the LCO global network.

image credits: SARA0

Astronomy projects such as the MeerKAT telescope are “not merely about advancing human understanding of the origins of the universe – it is about responding to the challenges that South Africans face now and into the future”.

**– SOUTH AFRICAN PRESIDENT CYRIL RAMAPHOSA,
STATE OF THE NATION ADDRESS, 2019**

GIRLS ASTRONOMY CAMP NIGERIA

Education levels in Nigeria are deeply impacted by gender inequalities. Over 5.5 million girls were out of school in Nigeria, according to a 2014 UNESCO report, and nearly two-thirds of women in the North West and North East regions have no education. The National Population Commission in Nigeria identified that drop-out rates are highest at the sixth grade of primary school and higher among girls than boys. Although social and economic factors also contribute to the problem, this project set out to improve the interest of girls in astronomy, space, and science topics.

In 2018, a one day astronomy awareness camp was held at the Obasanjo Space Center in Abuja, attended by 75 girls. Participants engaged in hands on activities, star gazing, solar observations, and a number of talks.

Three more camps were held in 2019 in Lokoja, Mararaba, and Abaji reaching over 700 female school students. Space and astronomy were excellent vehicles to spur their interest. Not only did these camps lead to better awareness of astronomy and space among the female students, it also 'normalized' the idea of female scientists

and engineers. The students interacted with potential role models and got to know their journey into STEM. It was one of the first OAD projects to primarily focus on the issue of gender inequality and has since been followed by several others.

The program was sponsored by OAD, Astronomers Without Borders, Universe Awareness, VIXEN Co. Ltd, National Institute for Astrophysics in Italy, and the Nigerian National Space Research & Development Agency.

“Why only support girls? Boys face challenges too, what about helping them?”

There are many, extremely severe challenges that affect the safety and opportunities of boys, particularly those in at-risk communities. However, when it comes to the issue of diversity and inclusion in STEM subjects, girls remain, by far, at a greater disadvantage than their male peers in pursuing these subjects. They remain more vulnerable to bullying and sexual violence, and are additionally at risk of teenage pregnancy.

The burden of domestic and child-raising duties also disproportionately fall on women. Combined with deeply ingrained gender stereotypes, this results in girls and women being extremely underrepresented in these fields.”

- ASTRO MOLO MHLABA

5 GENDER
EQUALITY

ASTRO MOLO MHLABA SOUTH AFRICA

In South Africa, girls in underserved communities are at great risk of physical and sexual violence, bullying, teenage pregnancy, drug and alcohol abuse, and gang culture at school. They constitute the majority of the drop-outs between Grade 6 and 9.

Molo Mhlaba is a network of local, low-fee, independent schools, catering to this vulnerable group in the country. The schools provide access to quality STEAM (Science, Technology, Engineering, Arts, Mathematics) education and career orientation, going beyond standard educational targets to strive for excellence and innovation.

Astronomy was chosen as a medium to encourage and support girls to pursue STEAM careers because it easily captures the imagination of children and enjoys a high profile in South Africa with growing availability of scholarships and jobs. Learning astronomy also provides skills which are sought after in the job market.

The astronomy program at the school consists of:

- an Astro Club: after-school program providing astronomy-based activities to primary school children on a weekly basis and
- an Astro Academy: astronomy lessons aimed at grade 11/12 female students from local high schools and recently-matriculated young women from the community. The latter are also trained to run the Astro Club as facilitators and receive a bursary for their work so that they have a continuous source of income while learning about astronomy and considering pursuit of a STEM degree. The facilitators have the option of obtaining free tutoring in maths and science.

All participants are taught and mentored by professional female astronomers, and provided with advice and support on how to pursue a STEM degree.

The project has been very successful in garnering attention among students and schools in the community and is planning for expansion. Its model and implementation have been praised by high level personnel in the South African government. Astro Molo Mhlaba received the "IAU Women and Girls in Astronomy" prize in 2019. It has been selected for a second round of funding by the OAD, and thus will continue to impact many more lives.

AMANAR: UNDER THE SAME SKY

ALGERIA & CANARY ISLANDS

The Amanar project taps into the inspiring potential of astronomy to promote peace, mutual understanding and a sense of global citizenship. Through a combination of astronomy activities, workshops and observations, the project promoted quality science education and enhanced resilience and self-empowerment among the children and teachers at Sahrawi refugee camps near Tindouf, Algeria.

The first phase of the project took place in July–August 2019 when children from the refugee camps went to the Canary islands as part of the “Holidays in Peace” program. They visited observatories to get a closer look at some of the telescopes and

participated in educational and outreach workshops. The last activity took place in Gran Canaria, where the Sahrawi and local children learned about astronomy and enjoyed the night sky together.

For the second phase, the project team members, a group of astronomers, communicators, film-makers, an ethnographer and other professionals, visited the Sahrawi refugee camps in Algeria. They conducted educational activities and teacher workshops, engaged with the community, and initiated a program on cultural astronomy to record the oral astronomy traditions of the Sahrawi people. Schools received kits with telescopes and educational resources. In total, the project reached 6 schools, 635 children and youth, 70 teachers and 150 members of the general public.

The Sahrawi community in the camps have been in a refugee status for more than 40 years. Astronomy not only offers respite from the hardships of everyday life but acts as a potential medium to develop skills and inculcate a vision for a peaceful future.

Funding and partnerships have been secured to run the summer program in the Canary Islands for at least 3 more years. The team is currently gathering support to visit the camps in Algeria on a regular basis in order to have a sustainable impact.

The project was funded by OAD and spearheaded by Galileomobile, a science education non-profit, in collaboration with the Instituto de Astrofísica de Canarias (IAC) and the Canary Association of Friendship with the Sahrawi People (ACAPS). Other partners included Cherenkov Telescope Array, Virgo Collaboration, Gran Telescopio de Canarias, Universe Awareness and Galileo teacher Training Program, IAU Office for Astronomy Outreach, Amnir Association, TITSA, Cielos de la Palma, CEIP en Arucas, Fundación Observatorio de Temisas, Agrupación Astronómica de Gran Canaria. It also received funding from the IAU100 anniversary program.

3 GOOD HEALTH AND WELL-BEING

IDP CHILDREN ASTRONOMY OUTREACH NIGERIA

Clashes between local farmers and cattle herdsman have displaced over 30,000 people in Nigeria.. This OAD project used astronomy as a tool to counsel, heal and educate children in an IDP (Internally Displaced People) camp, who were traumatised by such conflicts.

The selected target camp in Kuchingoro is located near Abuja Since the camp lacks formal schools, children receive minimal education, mostly taught by volunteers. The project team thus came up with the idea of using astronomy and space to create excitement for learning among the children.

The astronomy sessions were preceded by counselling sessions delivered by trained counsellors. They administered cognitive behavioural therapy which holds that by changing a person's thoughts and behaviours you can change their feelings. Cognitive behavioural assessments seek

to understand the problems that plague a patient and the underlying thoughts or behaviors that might be causing or worsening the problems. The objective was to enable the children to dream despite their current predicaments. The counselling was followed by astronomy activities and sky observations to get the children excited about opportunities and the outside world.

To alleviate the issue of access to learning materials, the team set up a learning hub at the camp. An unused shipping container was refurbished with a smart TV and charging port powered by solar panels, a hard drive with educational materials,

and video conferencing capabilities for continued interaction with the project team. The camp administration will be in charge of it and provide access to the children.

The learning hub goes beyond astronomy. It has become a place for the camp children to congregate and for other non-governmental organizations to run activities and even provide services such as health advice.

The project was funded by the OAD and provided support by the Nigerian Defense Space Administration. It has received another round of funding from the OAD for 2020.

Our Musical Universe

A sound-based planetarium show
exploring the rhythm and harmony
of the cosmos.

universe.utoronto.ca

4 QUALITY
EDUCATION

SYSTEM SOUNDS

CANADA/GLOBAL

SYSTEM Sounds is a science-art project that translates the rhythm and harmony of the cosmos into music and sound. A natural translation to music is possible in many astronomical systems due to the presence of resonances and periodic signals within and beyond the solar system. Through interactive apps, public exhibits, videos, and animations, the project makes astronomy more accessible to the public, including visually impaired audiences.

The project has created music from many astronomical systems and data. So far, they include: the motion of the solar system's terrestrial planets, Saturn's rings, Jupiter's moons, pulsars, blazars, exoplanets

(featured on NASA Astronomy Picture of the Day), the Apollo program, Hubble image of a galaxy cluster, and impacts on the Moon. Some of these sounds were integrated into a sound-based planetarium show called

“Our Musical Universe” with the support of the Ontario Arts Council. It was shown at the Dunlap Institute for Astronomy and Astrophysics, where it became Dunlap’s most successful show. The project also premiered a new planetarium experience called ‘One Sky’ that converted the thousands of twinkling stars in the night sky into music. Over 4500 visitors at Nuit Blanche Toronto walked underneath a large raised dome and experienced the night sky’s sights and sounds in real time.

Most recently, SYSTEM Sounds created an arcade-style exhibit, the Sonic Orbiter,

that lets one create music by steering the Lunar Reconnaissance Orbiter over the surface of the Moon. It was created as part of an artist residency at Toronto’s Museum of Contemporary Art and Ontario Science Centre.

The use of a popular, but unusual, medium such as music for science engagement has proved extremely effective with the videos and web-apps garnering millions of hits online, features on NASA, and press coverage on national and international media.

SIGN LANGUAGE UNIVERSAL ENCYCLOPEDIA DICTIONARY GLOBAL

Sign language is now officially practised in almost every country, but diverse heritages and different cultures independently developed specific signs to designate common objects or identical situations. This project developed the first international, comparative list of astronomical words in sign languages.

During the International Year of Astronomy in 2009, an encyclopedic dictionary of astronomy for French Sign Language was published, containing approximately 300 signs describing several classical celestial bodies and technical terms. The dictionary

was later translated into English with funding from the OAD.

Based on this experience, the IAU Commission for Astronomy Equity and Inclusion has embarked on a long-term

project to collect the different signs in several languages, starting with a list of the most common terms used in education and outreach. The signs in this list represent a collaboration between deaf communities,

educators, and astronomers all over the world and are meant to engage the deaf community in scientific discussion. The work is a joint ongoing effort between many individuals and organisations.

image credits: TED

“I want a field where we all work as equals, and where factors such as age, disability, gender and socio-economic status do not control my progress. I want my field not to underuse, misuse or neglect the human potential we all have for exploration and inquiry, and to trust that we all may contribute just as we are.”

**- DR. WANDA DIAZ-MERCED, ASTRONOMER AND ADVOCATE FOR INCLUSION
IN AN INTERVIEW WITH NATURE, 2019**

MAP OF OAD FUNDED PROJECTS 2013 - 2020

- Projects funded
- Regional Offices and Language Centers

AN

Europe

Asia

Africa

Australia

INDIAN OCEAN

*Astronomy for
Development*

science & innovation

Department:
Science and Innovation
REPUBLIC OF SOUTH AFRICA

SAAO
South African
Astronomical Observatory